

Investigating the Role of Topological Structures in a Many-Body System

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Abstract

The Axelrod model is an agent-based model composed of N F -dimensional vectors with each value taken from a range from 0 to $q - 1$. Agents are allowed to interact with their topological neighbors on a given network based on homophily-driven dynamical rules. This work studies the evolution of link densities of a toy model ($F = 2$) on a complete graph and a regular lattice. I wrote mean-field master equations and found that pairwise link dynamics are inherently dependent on higher-order triadic correlations, and the difference in topologies leads to a difference in local geometry and triad configurations. On a complete graph, the triad forms an interconnected triangle, perfectly closing the master equations, and all higher-order correlations canceled out due to symmetry. However, on a lattice, the triad forms a L-shape with a missing third link, forcing a closure approximation under mean-field assumptions, which introduces non-linear terms in the equations. Simulation results show a perfect alignment with theoretical predictions on complete graphs but a significant discrepancy on lattices. Further visualizations highlight that the dynamics on lattices are governed by a long-term coarsening process of cultural domains due to a path length $L \propto N^{1/2}$, whereas on complete graphs information spreads globally due to $L = 1$, causing it to behave nearly as a mean-field system.

1 Introduction

The field of sociophysics, which combines tools and methods from statistical physics to investigate social phenomena, has grown tremendously and is becoming an established research discipline [1] [2]. Sharing parallel ideas with complex systems, the field focuses on studying how nontrivial macroscopic behaviors emerge from microscopic interactions in a system. Modern sociophysics largely involves adapting an agent-based modeling methods inspired by statistical physics. A classic sociophysics ABM usually includes a group of agents. They are allowed to interact with their topological neighbors following a dynamics like Metropolis Monte-Carlo, simple neighbors' imitation, or majority

rules, among others. Such models are used to explore social phenomena such as cultural dissemination, opinion formation, political polarization, etc. This work focuses on the classic Axelrod model of cultural dissemination [3].

In the context of this model, culture is intended here as a set of beliefs or values that agents may mutually exchange. Specifically, an individual's culture is designed as a set of F variables with each being able to take a value from the range of 0 to $q - 1$. Starting from a random initial configuration, agents interact with their neighbors according to a probability equaling their cultural similarity. An interaction takes place following the social influence hypothesis, meaning that an agent would copy the feature of a selected neighbor after a conversation.

Traditional ABM models, including the one proposed by Axelrod, are usually lattice cellular automata. However, researchers in sociophysics have discovered that modifying the topological structure of the given interaction network of a system can lead to significant change of its dynamical behaviors [2]. Similar insights have been drawn from the statistical physics community focusing on the Axelrod model [4] [5] [6]. In previous works, the model has been studied on complete graphs, regular lattices, and random graphs. Although the problem is thoroughly analyzed both from both simulation and theoretical approaches for each of these networks, a unified explanation that explains why these differences arise has not yet been discussed. I tried to provide one by gathering and connecting former works focusing on link dynamics. Specifically, for the Axelrod model, on different types of topological networks, differences of the dynamical progression of link densities are observed. In this paper, I focused on complete graphs and regular lattices. Both a theoretical framework based on mean-field theories and simulation evidence are provided.

2 The model

Let us consider a system of N social agents sitting on a topological network. Each agent's cultural state is represented by an F -dimensional vector, namely : $P_n : (P_1, P_2, \dots, P_F)$ where each component resembles a specific feature or aspect of culture (sports, music, fashion, etc). Each cultural feature has a number of possible traits that range from 0 to $q - 1$. The dynamical rules of the model follow the concepts of homophily and social influence in real-world interactions, specifically:

- The probability of an interaction between two topologically connected agents is directly equal to their culture similarity, defined by $\frac{n}{F}$ where n represents the number of features the two agents shared in common.
- The agents would become more similar after an interaction. Precisely, an agent would copy one of its neighbor's feature that they previously don't share.

The system undergoes a non-equilibrium phase transition from a global consensus state (all agents share an identical culture configuration) to a multicul-

tural fragmented state depending on the parameter q . The specific value of q_c depends on F and also the network topology [2] [6] [5].

The density of active links has an advantage at quantifying the dynamics of the system while being analytically traceable [7] [8]. A link is simply a pair of topologically connected agents, and it is defined as active when the pair of agents shared $0 < n < F$ features in common. When density of active links reaches zero, meaning that every agent either share zero or all features with their neighbors, the system enters a frozen state where no further possible interactions could occur. In this work, I analyzed the link dynamics of the model on a complete graph and a two-dimensional lattice of a toy Axelrod model when $F = 2$.

3 Analytical formulation of topological differences

3.1 Master equations with higher order dependence

Given a homophily driven pairwise interaction, a change in the cultural state of an agent X due to a direct interaction with his partner produces not only an update in the similarity of the current link but also indirectly updates in the similarities of all the other pairs of agents which involve X . A master equation approach of describing this process is already established and widely utilized [9] [4] [10]. Here, I rewrite the indirect change terms for easier analysis of topological influences in later parts of this paper. Let P_m be the probability that a randomly selected bond belongs to type m (an m type bond refers to m features across the bond are equal and $F - m$ different). The evolution of P_m follows:

$$\frac{dP_m}{dt} = \sum_{k=1}^{F-1} \frac{k}{F} \left[P_k (\delta_{m,k+1} - \delta_{m,k}) + \tau \sum_{n=0}^F (Q_{nk\lambda} - Q_{mk\lambda'}) \right] \quad (1)$$

where τ is a constant that denotes the total number of links experiencing indirect changes, usually expressed by the degree of a node or the lattice coordination number. $Q_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ is a three degree probability distribution, specifically:

$$Q_{\alpha\beta\gamma} = P(\text{sim}(X, Y) = \alpha, \text{sim}(X, Z) = \beta, \text{sim}(Y, Z) = \gamma) \quad (2)$$

This equation describes how the number of bonds of type m is affected by the dynamics: $P_k k/F$ is the probability to select a bond of type k and one of the k features which are equal across it. During an update (a direct change), if $k = m - 1$ a new bond of type m is created whereas if $k = m$ one bond of type m is deleted.

Alternatively, the net indirect change is a combination of indirect changes that happen at the smallest interaction unit - a three agent triad of a network

- regardless of the topological structures. Let us consider the triad of agent X , Y and Z where XZ is connected by a type $k = 0$ bond and is adjacent to XY which is connected by a type $k = 1$ bond. Without the loss of generality, we can write X and Y as $(0, \sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_F)$ and $(0, 0, \dots, 0)$ with $\sigma_j \neq 0$. Agent Z , who share zero features with X takes the form $(\sigma'_1, \sigma'_2, \dots, \sigma'_F)$ where $\sigma'_1 \neq 0$ and $\sigma_j \neq \sigma'_j$. When the XY bond is chosen in an update, $\sigma_2 \rightarrow 0$. The neighboring XZ 0 bond can become a 1 bond if $\sigma'_2 = 0$. Or in other words, it relies on the node-node similarity status between Y and Z . Therefore, an indirect link update, which originally only involves two nodes, turns out to be dependent on the higher order XYZ triad, and the probability that an indirect change occurs equal to the probability that a specific configuration of XYZ appears. This explains the Q terms in the rhs of (1).

3.2 Topological-dependent closures

On a network, when two sites i and j are topological neighbors, the following relationship between node-node similarities and link variables always holds true:

$$P(sim(i, j) = k) = P_k \quad (3)$$

As a result, for Q , if all three sites of the triad are interconnected, it can naturally be expressed in terms of the global link variable P , leading (2) to be perfectly closed. This is the case on a complete graph where the clustering coefficient C equals one.

On a CG, [10] proposed a similarity vector description of the model where a link between a pair of agents is written as a F -dimensional binary vector that has an X in the place where they share a cultural feature and 0 otherwise. For $F = 2$, a given similarity vector can be in one of the four states: $P_0 = [0, 0]$, $P_{1a} = [X, 0]$, $P_{1b} = [0, X]$ or $P_2 = [X, X]$.

To illustrate this, consider the following two agent pairs $[(1, 2), (1, 3)]$ and $[(2, 2), (2, 3)]$, both are connected by a 1 bond, but under similarity vector descriptions, the first link (two agents sharing the first feature in common) is classified as type $1a$, and the second one is defined as type $1b$.

This method helps us enumerate possible configurations of Q in (1) in a much easier way. Substituting all parameters gives the following set of master equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dP_0}{dt} &= \frac{N-2}{4}(P_{1a}P_{1b}P_0 + P_{1a}P_{1b}P_0 - P_{1a}P_{1b}P_0 - P_{1a}P_{1b}P_0) \\
\frac{dP_{1a}}{dt} &= \frac{-P_{1a}}{2} + \frac{N-2}{4}(P_{1a}P_{1b}P_0 + P_{1a}^2P_2 - P_{1a}^2P_2 - P_{1a}P_{1b}P_0) \\
\frac{dP_{1b}}{dt} &= \frac{-P_{1b}}{2} + \frac{N-2}{4}(P_{1a}P_{1b}P_0 + P_{1b}^2P_2 - P_{1b}^2P_2 - P_{1a}P_{1b}P_0) \\
\frac{dP_2}{dt} &= \frac{P_{1a} + P_{1b}}{2} + \frac{N-2}{4}(P_{1a}^2P_2 + P_{1b}^2P_2 - P_{1b}^2P_2 - P_{1a}^2P_2)
\end{aligned}$$

where N is the total number of nodes on a network. The $(N-2)$ factor, corresponding to τ in (1), gives the total number of indirect links that participate in the dynamics. As we can see in these equations, all the non-linear terms canceled out, and the set of equations can therefore be explicitly solved:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dP_0}{dt} &= 0 \rightarrow P_0(t) = P_0(t=0) \\
\frac{dP_1}{dt} &= \frac{-P_1}{2} \rightarrow P_1(t) = P_1(t=0)e^{-\frac{t}{2}} \\
\frac{dP_2}{dt} &= \frac{dP_1}{2} \rightarrow P_2(t) = 1 - P_0(t=0) - P_1(t=0)e^{-\frac{t}{2}}
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

The set of equations agrees with the normalization $\frac{dP_0}{dt} + \frac{dP_1}{dt} + \frac{dP_2}{dt} = 0$ of a closed system, and simulation results perfectly aligned with the theoretical solutions, shown in fig.1. The system size does not play a role for the dynamics once time is rescaled as $\Delta t = \frac{1}{M}$ where M is the total number of bonds in the system. Moreover, besides determining the initial values for the three type of bonds, the parameter q does not influence the dynamics.

Figure 1: Simulation results of link dynamics versus theoretical predictions when $F = q = 2$ on complete graph. Time is rescaled as $\Delta t = \frac{1}{M}$ where M is the total number of bonds in the system

For a lattice, link dynamics exhibits a completely different pattern. Let us still consider the $X - Y - Z$ triad. On a complete graph, all agents are connected. The triplet we're focusing therefore forms a perfect triangle, whereas on a lattice, the three nodes are only connected into a L-shape since Z and Y are not topological neighbors, meaning that a link does not exist between them. Hence, we can not use a global link marginal to portray the status of the pair.

In order to close (1), an approximation is necessary. When $F = 2$, for a 1-0-1 triad, X , Y and Z take the general form $(0, \sigma_2)$, $(0, 0)$ and (σ'_1, σ'_2) . The probability that σ'_2 and Y shares the second feature 0 is given by $\frac{q-1}{(q-1)^2} = \frac{1}{(q-1)}$. Define $\rho = \frac{1}{q-1}$. The expression of ρ is only true when $t = 0$, yet under a mean-field spirit, an assumption is made here that ρ stays constant during the dynamics [4].

After introducing ρ , different Q triads can be now calculated. Instead of similar vectors, a simpler way to enumerate all combinations is to write everything in terms of transition probabilities. Let $\theta_{m,n}^k$ be the probability of an m bond changing into a n bond when an adjacent k bond experienced an direct update. For the 1-0-1 triad, we have $P_1 P_0 \theta_{0,1}^1 = Q_{101}$.

We can now re-write (1) as:

$$\frac{dP_m}{dt} = \sum_{k=1}^{F-1} \frac{k}{F} P_k \left[\delta_{m,k+1} - \delta_{m,k} + (g-1) \sum_{n=0}^F \left(P_n \theta_{n,m}^{(k)} - P_m \theta_{m,n}^{(k)} \right) \right] \quad (5)$$

With ρ , the transition probabilities can be obtained from pure combinatorics:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{0,0}^{(1)} &= 1 - \rho \\ \theta_{0,1}^{(1)} &= \rho \\ \theta_{0,2}^{(1)} &= 0 \\ \theta_{1,0}^{(1)} &= \frac{1}{2} \\ \theta_{1,1}^{(1)} &= \frac{1 - \rho}{2} \\ \theta_{1,2}^{(1)} &= \frac{\rho}{2} \\ \theta_{2,1}^{(1)} &= 1 \\ \theta_{2,0}^{(1)} &= 0 \\ \theta_{2,2}^{(1)} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Expanding (5) and then substitute the values, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dP_0}{dt} &= \frac{(g-1)}{2} P_1 \left(-\rho P_0 + \frac{P_1}{2} \right) \\ \frac{dP_1}{dt} &= \frac{-P_1}{2} + \frac{(g-1)}{2} P_1 \left(\rho P_0 - \frac{1+\rho}{2} + P_2 \right) \\ \frac{dP_2}{dt} &= \frac{P_1}{2} + \frac{(g-1)}{2} P_1 \left(\frac{\rho}{2} P_1 - P_2 \right) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where g is the lattice coordination number that takes a value of 4 on a 2D lattice. This equation also fulfills the normalization condition.

At this point, the role of topologies in the dynamics of the system is clear. The Axelrod model is based on local updating rules, and different topological structures created different kinds of local geometries which eventually leads to a difference in macroscopic behaviors of the system.

4 Validity of mean-field descriptions on different topologies

Figure 2: Comparisons of master equation solutions and simulation results for the model under $F = 2$ and $q = 2, 4, 8$. A log-scale for density is applied for a better display of the result

Numerical solutions of P_1 in (7) are presented in fig.2. It is obvious that as q increases, the non-monotonic behavior of solutions becomes more and more obvious, which is systematically proved in [4]. This result shows that mean-field approaches on lattices lead to an inaccurate description of the system.

To illustrate this, on a complete graph, the network itself is a mean field. A direct update of one link will affect all the other links since every agent is connected with each other. The dynamics itself is global, whereas on a grid a change in $X - Z$ only affects the three other links. Information only spreads locally. This can be quantified by the path length L , which gives the shortest steps it takes for one agent to reach another in a given network. In the context of link dynamics, when given an agent X , only agents separated by a path length of 1 with X would get affected by indirect and direct link changes. On a CG, every pair of agents has $L = 1$, whereas on a lattice where $L \propto N^{1/2}$ for a pair, only $(g - 1)$ pairs fulfill the requirement. Evidence is also provided in fig.3, where a rapid decay in density is observed on a CG, corresponding to fast global changes, while on a lattice the time it takes for density to reach its

steady state is long, corresponding to the long-term coarsening process.

Figure 3: Simulation results of lattices when $q = 8$. Result on CG is also presented for comparison.

Alternatively, introducing the concepts of cultural domains is particularly effective when it comes to explaining the difference of global versus local information spread. Simulation snapshots of the model when $F = q = 2$ are provided below.

Axelrod Model on 2D Grid (L=50, F=2, Q=2)
Formation of Cultural Domains

(a) Simulation snapshots on a lattice

(b) Simulation snapshots on a complete graph

Figure 4: Simulation snapshots of the model on different topologies when $F = q = 2$.

The spatial structure of the formations of large cultural domains on a lattice is obvious. Throughout the dynamics, one can clearly identify the trend of the domains expanding while merging smaller domains. However, on the contrary, the dominant culture on the complete graph (the purple one) is not formed through a coarsening process. Instead, it suddenly flashes from the background, and the reason behind this is that agents that obtained such type of culture are located at every corner of the network, and the structure of CG allows them to interact with each other. So essentially, numerous micro-domains at different places are expanding simultaneously, which provides an evidence of why mean-field assumptions work so well on a CG. Essentially, the dynamics itself is a randomly mixing process. However, on a lattice. The theory fails to predict the coarsening behavior and neglects spatial correlations.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, I analyzed how topologies play a role in shaping the dynamics of a classic social influence model by focusing on the evolution of its link density. I started by introducing mean-field master equations to quantify the dynamics. The derivation highlights that link dynamics, which only involves a two-degree node interaction, are dependent on a higher-degree triad, which is the first place where topologies matter. Specifically, different topologies determine different local geometries of the network and therefore influence the structure of the triplet. On a complete graph where the triad forms a perfect triangle, equation (1) is perfectly closed, and in a toy model of $F = 2$ all cubic terms cancel out. Conversely, the triad forms an incomplete L-shape on the lattice, which requires closure approximations that produce high-order nonlinear terms.

My further simulation results show that the discrepancy does not just stem from differences in local structures. Due to the innate properties of the networks and the interaction rules of the model, cultural symbols disseminate globally on CGs whereas on lattices, they form spatially correlated domains and experience a coarsening process, both of which are important elements of the system that mean-field theories failed to predict. While such approaches have shown to be effective at highlighting transitions of the system's properties with respect to its key parameters, they struggle to provide insights on the model's dynamics. For more accurate descriptions, techniques that go beyond mean-field theories are necessary. This involves adding reaction and diffusion terms in (1), and perhaps utilizing dynamic renormalization group methods.

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